

A Study of the Dependence of the Slope S_v of the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} Curves. Part III : Ethanol-Water Mixtures

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The effect of the dielectric constant of the medium on the nature (positive and negative) of the slope S_v of the apparent molar volume, ϕ_v , vs. \sqrt{C} curves of some tetraalkylammonium iodides has been examined in this communication using ethanol-water mixtures as mixtures of known but different dielectric constants. The negative slope for the Pr_4NI and Bu_4NI salts becomes positive around 64 and 58 dielectric constants respectively. These values are very close to those for dioxane-water and methanol-water systems. The results of these communications taken together seem to indicate the dominant role of the dielectric constant of the medium in controlling the nature of the slope.

IN continuation with the earlier communications^{1,2} from this laboratory, dealing with the effect of the dielectric constant of the medium on the slope S_v of the Masson's equation viz.,

$$\phi_v = \phi_o + S_v \sqrt{C}$$

ϕ_v and ϕ_o being the apparent molar volumes at dilution 'v' and at infinite dilution respectively, in the case of some tetraalkylammonium salts in dioxane-water¹ and methanol-water² mixtures, the studies have been extended to ethanol-water mixtures with a view to examine whether replacing dioxane and methanol by ethanol will have any significant effect on the slope. The dielectric constant of ethanol-water mixtures of different ethanol contents have been reported in the literature.³ These mixtures have been used here as solvents of different dielectric constants.

Experimental

Absolute alcohol ($\approx 99.5\%$) was obtained from double distilled rectified spirit in the usual manner. Further purification of absolute alcohol thus obtained was carried out as per procedure given below :

5 gms of magnesium turnings and 0.5 gm (approx.) of iodine were placed in a flask to which 75 ml of absolute alcohol were added. The flask was heated gently until all magnesium had dissolved. To this 900 ml more of absolute alcohol were added and the mixture was refluxed for 30 minutes. Alcohol was then distilled off and was taken to be 99.95% pure ethyl alcohol and was used with conductivity water for preparing mixtures of known

dielectric constant³. Mixtures containing 9.67%, 19.86%, 34.47%, 42.15% and 54.23% by weight of alcohol, having respectively the dielectric constants at 25° as 72.99, 67.08, 58.37, 53.60 and 46.66 were prepared and were used for preparing solutions. Tetraalkylammonium iodides were purified in the

Fig. 1—Apparent molar volume, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves for Me_4NI in different ethanol-water mixtures at 40°.

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usual manner⁴. Solutions of these salts in various mixtures were prepared and their densities at 40° were determined in the manner described previously². Due to solubility restrictions, investigation had to be confined to smaller members viz., Me₄NI, Et₄NI, Pr₄NI and Bu₄NI, of the P₄NI series of salts the larger ones being almost insoluble.

Results and Discussion

From the density data, thus obtained, the apparent molar volumes ϕ_v of different salts in various mixtures were calculated and the ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves were drawn (Figs 1-4).

Fig. 2—Apparent molal volume, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves for Et₄NI in different ethanol-water mixtures at 40°.

Fig. 4—Apparent molal volume, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves for Bu₄NI in different ethanol-water mixtures at 40°.

Fig. 3—Apparent molal volume, ϕ_v vs \sqrt{C} curves for Pr₄NI in different ethanol-water mixtures at 40°.

It may be noted from the figures that for the Me₄NI and Et₄NI salts, the slope is positive although it appears to decrease with the increase in the dielectric constant of the medium; for Pr₄NI and Bu₄NI salts, the positive slope at the lower dielectric constant becomes actually negative at higher dielectric constants. This fact is brought out more explicitly by plotting the slope S_v against the dielectric constant (Fig. 5).

It is interesting to note from Figure 5 that the slope S_v decreases smoothly with the increase in the dielectric constant. The change-over of the slope from positive to a negative value for the Pr₄NI and Bu₄NI salts, occurs around dielectric constants as 63-64 and 58-59 respectively. The slopes for Me₄NI and Et₄NI remain positive even at 80 (pure water) although extrapolation of the respective curves give 100 and 89 as the dielectric constants at the transition point in the two cases. Compared at these values, the same point for these respective salts occurs in dioxane-water mixtures around 100

(estimated), 74 (estimated), 68 and 57 and in ethanol-water mixtures around 90 (estimated), 86 (estimated), 63 and 58. It is interesting to note that these transition point dielectric constants, as observed for Pr_4NI and Bu_4NI , in all the three solvent mixtures, are very nearly the same although the estimated values for the similar transition points for Me_4NI and Et_4NI differ somewhat in the three systems and appear to be erratic.

Fig. 5—Dependence of the slope S_v on the Dielectric Constant, ϵ in Ethanol-water mixtures at 40° .

The results seem to suggest that the constituents of solvent medium appear to play only a secondary role in determining the nature of the slope S_v (positive or negative); it is only the dielectric constant of the medium which matters.

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